

Delving into circular consumption: circular attitudes and their influence on consumers' behavior across the product lifecycle¹

Abstract

This study explores the dynamic and multidimensional realm of circular consumption, emphasizing the relevance of a lifecycle perspective in understanding consumer behaviors within the circular economy. Going beyond previous research focused on specific actions such as recycling or purchasing second-hand products, we advocate for a broader understanding of consumer choices across a product's lifecycle. Drawing on attitudes theory, we employ item response theory (IRT) models to unveil latent attitudes reflecting diverse circular consumer behaviors. These attitudes, inferred from manifested actions across different product lifecycle stages, include environmental-centric, resources-centric and societal-centric circular attitudes. Overall, the study involves a representative sample of 5,124 respondents in five European countries. Our findings highlight the complexity of consumer motivations in the circular economy, revealing different attitude-behavior links. This research contributes to a nuanced understanding of circular consumption, emphasizing the importance of a lifecycle approach, propelling the development of robust measurement scales of circular consumer actions.

Keywords: Circular Attitudes, Circular Consumption, Item Response Theory, Consumer Behavior, Attitude-Behavior link

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1 Introduction

The circular economy represents a multidimensional paradigm fostering environmentally responsible behaviors, notably through lifecycle thinking (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2020; European Environment Agency, 2021; Gomes et al., 2022). Consumers, acting as key contributors, translate circular economy principles into conscious behaviors that extend across the product lifecycle, encompassing stages like use and disposal (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2020; European Environment Agency, 2021; Gomes et al., 2022). The emerging term, circular consumption, encapsulates this holistic approach (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2020; European Environment Agency, 2021; Gomes et al., 2022), moving beyond conventional "green" or "ethical" labels during purchase.

Such a burgeoning concept of circular consumption encompasses a comprehensive system of decisions and activities, namely, choices (Sun et al., 2016; Woodside and Dubelaar, 2002). This wide array of choices unfolds across various circular consumption stages (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Bakker et al., 2014; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013; Hollander et al., 2017; Piscicelli and Ludden, 2016; Weelden et al., 2016).

At the acquisition stage, for instance, consumer choices impact product circularity, introducing dilemmas rooted in conflicting behaviors (e.g., re-buying conflicting with renting or sharing). These complexities arise from aligning choices with values, lifestyle, and broader sustainability goals, reflecting the intricate landscape of circular consumption. Environmental attitudes and non-environmental factors influence sustainable consumption, underscoring the need for a nuanced understanding (Testa et al., 2021). And this thread of choices carries over through the product's consumption and up to its final disposal (Gomes et al., 2022; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017), with consumers playing a pivotal role across the whole product life cycle (Gomes et al., 2022; Di Iorio et al., 2022).

Previous studies on circular consumption have frequently overlooked the breadth of behaviors that consumers can adopt, considering the entire product life cycle (Testa et al., 2020). Many studies have predominantly concentrated on specific actions, such as purchasing recycled or second-hand products (Pretner et al., 2021; Rausch and Kopplin, 2021; Polyportis et al., 2022), sharing items (Ter Huurne et al., 2017), buying refurbished goods (Abbey et al., 2015; Bigliardi et al., 2022), or engaging in recycling activities (Tonglet et al., 2004; Aboelmaged, 2021). There is a pressing need for further advancement by emphasizing the multidimensional nature of the circular paradigm, which offers consumers several alternatives to contribute to the efficient utilization of resources within the entire societal-economic system.

The array of options also accentuates the diverse drivers that may influence an individual's choice among them. Recently, a substantial body of

empirical findings on the drivers of circular consumption has emerged (Shevchenko et al., 2023). Many studies rely on rational decision-making processes, such as the Theory of Reasoned Action and the Theory of Planned Behavior (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 2001), highlighting the significance of information (Di Iorio et al., 2022), personal values (Tan et al., 2022; Riva et al., 2022), beliefs and attitudes (Testa et al., 2020; Apaoulaza et al., 2022; Guimarães et al., 2023). While many studies have focused on the latter, particularly emphasizing the importance of environmental attitudes, this approach risks oversimplifying the complexity of motivations behind circular behaviors. Notwithstanding such a mushrooming literature resonating with circular consumption, a critical review of such empirical literature reveals open issues requiring further development. In particular, it is important to explore more profoundly the motivations behind all circular behaviours in order to identify the role of different attitudes, their complementarity and potential divergences.

To make this point, conversely to what the bulk of studies has done so far, this research defines the circular attitudes as unobserved (latent) characteristics influencing consumers' actions in various circular consumption stages. Adopting an inductive approach through exploratory item response theory (IRT) models, the study develops implicit (reflective) measures of the latent attitudes underlying circular consumer behaviours. As the type and frequency of consumers' actions change according to individual attitudes, abilities, and value structures, the adoption of a reflective measurement approach through IRT models, allows assessing attitudes through a set of questions regarding individual actions or observed behaviors, rather than directly measuring linear combinations of consumers' beliefs or future intentions through attitude scales.

Over the recent years, IRT models have become popular due to its benefits in assessing indirect (implicit) measures of latent characteristics – namely attitudes, abilities, beliefs, or behavioral characteristics (e.g. purchasing tendency). IRT made his appearance in several fields: in economics, detecting situations of need or deprivation (Szeles and Fusco, 2013), in medicine, identifying complex health conditions (Prenovost et al., 2018), in marketing (De Jong et al., 2008), organizational research (Foster et al., 2017), and strategic management, to capture CSR-related behavior in organizations (Carroll et al., 2016); accordingly, it is reasonable to assert that its application might stretch over circular consumption, revitalizing the way attitudinal drivers to such a multifaceted array of behaviors like the circular consumption have been assessed so far.

The research adheres to a commitment to rigor and incorporates a replication strategy for robustness and external validity. Study 1 explores circular behaviours in the clothing product category over the Italian population while Study 2 verifies the solidity of the findings, replicating the same approach to the other four major European Union countries such as Spain, France, Poland and Germany. Analyses are conducted over a sample of 5,124 respondents, representative of the population of the above-

mentioned countries. Examining observed consumer actions patterns based on a starting list of 30 items encompassing circular actions throughout a product's lifecycle, the research investigates whether different attitudes reflect varied value structures, epitomizing the interaction of diverse and not always convergent factors influencing a set of circular behaviors. Specifically, three distinct latent attitudes emerge: environmental-centric, resources-centric, and societal-centric attitudes. Additionally, this study emphasizes a lifecycle perspective that extends the concept of consumer behavior to further stages, including reuse, sharing, second-hand practices, product use, repair, and post-use considerations (circular consumer behavior). By embracing and understanding lifecycle thinking, consumers become aware of the need for coherent behaviors along the product lifecycle, enabling them to undertake future actions coherently and potentially change their traditional habits.

This study makes three significant contributions. First, it advances the discourse on the rational drivers of circular behaviors (Abbasi et al., 2022; Rausch and Kopplin, 2021) by highlighting the coexistence of several attitudes that reflect diverse and not always convergent needs and value structures. Second, surpassing a reductionist approach that separately considers circular behaviors, the study underscores the multidimensional nature of the circular paradigm, which generates a wide array of behaviors that individuals may adopt to contribute to a circular transition. Finally, the study contributes to the ongoing debate on developing comprehensive measurement scales (Sudbury-Riley and Kohlbacker, 2016; Di Iorio et al., 2023) capable of holistically capturing circular actions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The circular transition and the increased complexity in consumers' behaviours

The heightened focus on eco-friendly consumption models, exemplified by the circular economy, has precipitated a profound shift in consumer behavior. Some authors even characterize this shift as a consumption "system," encompassing a set of activities, decisions, and behaviors that span product purchase and use to satisfy consumer needs (Sun et al., 2016; Woodside and Dubelaar, 2002). Circular consumption, aligned with the principles of the circular economy, is defined as the set of consumers' activities and decisions that follow a multidimensional and holistic approach (Gomes et al., 2022; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017).

The pivotal role of consumers in steering society towards a circular economy through circular consumption cannot be underestimated. Their choices and behaviors throughout the product life cycle, from acquisition to disposition, play a crucial role in shaping a sustainable future. In essence, consumers are key actors in the transition to a circular economy (Gomes et al., 2022; Testa et al., 2020).

In a circular economy, consumers are expected to perform a series of behaviors that enable circular consumption. By drawing on the tradition of 'R' models and waste hierarchies, for each consumption stage more circular consumption behaviors can be ascribed (Kirchherr et al., 2017). These stages do not represent any hierarchy but are extrapolated from business models and practices suggested in literature (Bakker et al., 2014; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013; Piscicelli and Ludden, 2016; Weelden et al., 2016). They represent a sample set of behaviors that require active involvement or initiation by consumers.

At the acquisition stage, consumers have a range of choices that significantly impact the circularity of a product. They can choose to re-buy items, promoting a recycling loop, or opt for renting and sharing, reducing overall resource consumption. This underscores the idea that consumers, through their choices, can contribute to the circular transition in diverse ways.

As consumers appropriate and utilize products, their actions set the circular economy in motion. Retaining and properly maintaining possessions prolongs their lifespan, aligning with circular principles. Repairing items instead of discarding them contributes to resource conservation. Additionally, paying for high-quality, long-lasting products nudges companies towards this kind of production. This is the circular consumption in the making.

In the stages of appreciation, devaluation, and divestment, consumers face a plethora of decisions (European Environment Agency, 2021; Niinimäki, 2017). They may choose to value experiences over possessions (appreciation), actively devalue products that do not align with circular principles, or divest from items that no longer serve a purpose. Each decision has implications for the circular economy (European Environment Agency, 2021, Poore and Nemecek, 2018).

The disposition stage introduces actions like returning, re-selling, and relinquishing products. Consumers may choose to return items at the end of their life cycle, engage in re-selling to extend the product's usability, or relinquish items responsibly. These actions directly impact waste reduction and resource efficiency.

However, the complexity arises from the fact that these diverse actions are not always harmonious (Filippas et al., 2020). For instance, the decision to re-buy conflicts with the concept of renting or sharing. This conundrum sparks dilemmas in the minds of consumers (Ali et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2023). They grapple with choices that align with their values, lifestyle, and the broader societal goals of sustainability.

The heart of the matter lies in the dilemmas that consumers face due to the overlapping nature of these actions. For instance, a consumer may wrestle with the decision to rent a product for immediate needs or purchase it for long-term use (Filippas et al., 2020). Similarly, the choice between retaining and repairing a product versus discarding it for an upgraded version presents a dilemma rooted in the tension between emotional attachment and technological progress (Jiménez and Voss, 2014; Hirschman, 1980.).

In conclusion, consumers wield significant influence in steering society towards a circular economy. The myriad actions they can undertake throughout a product's life cycle provide ample opportunities for contribution. However, the inherent conflicts and dilemmas between these actions underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of consumer behavior in the context of circular consumption.

2.2 Untangling the complexity of circular consumption: A spotlight on attitudes

In the realm of circular consumption, numerous studies have delved into the factors influencing behaviors, revealing the intricate interplay of attitudes in predicting rational actions (Testa et al., 2021; Di Iorio et al., 2022; Hosta and Zabkar, 2020). For instance, research by Testa and colleagues (2021) has shed light on the nuanced motivations driving individuals to embrace circular practices. According to them, while environmental attitudes remain a key predictor for sustainable consumption, attitudes towards non-environmental factors, such as lifestyle traits and collectivism, also play a significant role in influencing actual purchase behavior.

In investigating the interplay between attitudes and behaviors, various studies adopt a methodological, deductive rationale that unfolds through the product lifecycle. This approach involves asking respondents to rate their level of agreement on both their attitudes (predictors) and behaviors (outcomes). This method has been applied broadly to sustainable behaviors, now collectively known as circular consumption.

Examining the purchase stage, attitudinal drivers are investigated by mainly focusing on the environmental issues, personal inclinations towards the objects of study or personal values (Ali et al., 2019; Bigliardi et al., 2022; Hazen et al., 2017; Tong et al. 2023). For instance, Apauolaza et al. (2022) delved into the factors influencing the acquisition of sustainable clothing. Their analysis included conspicuous consumption motives, environmental concern, perceived consumer effectiveness, trust in sustainable clothing brands, and perceived greenwashing. Similarly, Testa and colleagues (2021) experimentally investigated customer attitudes towards various types of sustainable packaging, assessing their impact on purchase intention, whether the packaging was recycled, compostable, or made from virgin plastic.

Numerous sheards of evidence also emerge from studies focused on further stages of consumption life cycle, which keep environmental related attitude as a pivotal driver. For instance, transitioning to the consumption phase, De Guimarães et al. (2023) explored the purchase of remanufactured products, such as smartphones, considering utilitarian and hedonic dimensions of consumption alongside environmental awareness. Similarly, Riva et al. (2022) focused on green consumerism, evaluating sustainable restaurants by assessing green perceived value and green perceived quality. Finally, in the post-consumption stage, Rizomyliotis et al. (2021) examined

green consumption values and their moderating effect on brand loyalty concerning brand experiences and brand personality.

It is worth noting that most of these studies have drawn on rational predictive models, like the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (e.g., Tong et al., 2023), or simply parts of it [e.g., De Guimarães et al. (2023), Hazen et al. (2017) to name a few]. However, while these studies underscore the importance of attitudes, they also reveal a significant limitation in their explanatory power and accountability regarding the transition to circular consumption (Singh and Giacosa, 2019).

This is due to their tendency to oversimplify the complexity inherent in circular consumption behaviors, a complexity uncovered in the preceding paragraph. The essence of the complexity inherent in circular consumption stems from the dilemmas that arise at each stage of a product's lifecycle. In this context, various disposal alternatives not only compete but often conflict with each other, influencing consumer choices (European Environment Agency, 2021). This complexity becomes evident only when we consider all the different stages throughout the product lifecycle. Understanding this is crucial to realizing that the drivers (e.g., attitudes) influencing the various choices made across the product lifecycle can vary at each stage.

For example, buying brand-new, sustainable-cotton-fiber clothing might be prompted by some lurking attitude which might be different than those occurring in the next stage of the product's life cycle, like swapping the garment when it is approaching its end of life. Moreover, the selection of one option instead of another one may be related to different personal inclinations that deserves an explorative approach. That paves the way for new deductive studies.

Up to date, indeed, very few studies have attempted to measure attitudes by adopting reflective measurement approaches based on observed consumers' behaviors. At the forefront of such an approach stands the work done by Minton and colleagues (2017) on the Priming Theory, elaborated upon the ABC model of attitudes (Breckler, 1984). However, this work does not seem to include a theory-driven discussion about the connection between (latent) consumer attitudes and (observed) behaviors. The main focus is on the concept of consumer priming, including various types of priming (affective, behavioral, cognitive) and their effects in the context of consumer behavior. Although the authors examined how different types of priming influence consumers' attitudes and behaviors, the study does not provide a theory-driven exploration of the relationship between these two constructs in by applying social psychology principles in the marketing context. Yet, the study paves the way for further research to come along this new way of reasoning.

In essence, the call for an exploratory study based on the theoretical foundations of attitudes (Bohner and Dickel, 2011) and the adoption of consistent (reflective) measurement approaches emerges as a necessity in understanding the complexities of circular consumption behaviors and, in particular, whether and how different patterns of observed circular

consumption may reflect differential value structures and the resulting latent (circular) attitudes. As IRT-based measures reflect the individual level association between the attitude object (the selection of different actions) and the valued attributes of each action, specific patterns of individual actions along the product lifecycle represent the result of a rational evaluation based on the individual level of the latent attitude(s). Hence, such a study would go beyond explicit, formative measurement approaches of circular attitudes based on linear combinations of attitude scales items, and approach circular attitudes in a reflective manner by delving into patterns of observed circular behaviors and underlining the types of behaviors pursued by consumers with low and high level of circular attitudes. By adopting a retrospective, explorative perspective, this research contributes to a theory-driven, nuanced understanding of the psychological factors (attitudes and the related value structures) influencing the choices consumers make in the ever-evolving landscape of circular consumption.

3. Research design, data and methodology

3.1 Research design

Drawing inspiration from the methodology frequently employed in qualitative research to enhance the robustness and external validity of emerging findings (Yin, 2003; 2004), our research design was based on a replication strategy. We executed two distinct field studies in separate contexts, employing an identical conceptual framework and survey design for replication purposes. In a first stage, we implemented a survey based on questionnaires, targeting a representative sample of Italian citizens. This study (Study 1) aimed to investigate the adoption of circular behaviors focusing on a specific product category—clothing products. This choice was motivated by the recognition that the clothing industry represents a pivotal component of the complex landscape of the circular transition (McKinsey, 2020). In this context, individual consumers might engage in a variety of actions contributing to the circular transition, such as sharing, purchasing second-hand clothing, responsibly using items to extend their lifespan, or engaging in activities like repairing or repurposing (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021). The wide context of clothing goods provided an ideal research setting, allowing the exploration of extended consumers' behaviors going beyond the simple act of purchase, and including use, after use and product disposal, such as sharing or use of second-hand product as well as repair and reuse behaviors (Testa et al., 2020). This approach allowed to align our empirical setting with the multifaceted nature of the circular economy concept (Murray et al., 2017).

In a subsequent phase, to validate the robustness of the initial findings, we opted to replicate the established conceptual framework by submitting the same questionnaire to representative samples of consumers beyond Italy,

namely in France, Germany, Spain, and Poland (Study 2). Expanding the geographical scope of the sample from Italy to the four largest countries in the European Union allowed us to systematically assess the reliability of our findings in the presence of cultural differences across European countries.

3.2. Data collection

In the two studies, we employed the same commercial data provider to administer the questionnaire to a representative sample of the population aged 18-75 in the respective countries under consideration.

While the validity of data collected through questionnaires is a topic of extensive debate (Donaldson and Grant-Vallone, 2002), our questionnaire development process considered potential issues associated with self-reported data (Podsakoff et al., 2003). This approach aimed to achieve alignment between self-reported behaviors and actual conduct, a correlation recently affirmed by Testa et al. (2019) in the context of green consumption.

To develop the survey instruments, we employed a dual approach. Initially, we grounded our measurements in an extensive literature review to incorporate insightful stimuli. Subsequently, we engaged experts from both the academic and practitioner realms, to ensure content validity. Additionally, we involved potential respondents to ensure the effectiveness of the procedures adopted for mitigating common method variance bias (King and Bruner, 2000; Tourangeau and Yan, 2007).

This approach effectively prevented the inclusion of vague or complex concepts and sentences, as well as unfamiliar or ambiguous words in the formulation of questions. The questions were deliberately crafted to be simple, concise, and precise, with specific identification of behaviors to mitigate recall bias. To address acquiescence bias, we varied both scales and verbal labels. Lastly, participant anonymity was unequivocally guaranteed throughout the study.

The questionnaire focused on clothing products and was submitted to a representative sample of population from the five largest countries in European Union (i.e., France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Poland) (World Bank, 2020). The questionnaire was drafted by a team of five researchers with different background guided by the first author.

To assess circular consumer behaviors beyond the simple acquisition of new fashion items, we integrated an in-depth examination of previously affirmed measures related to sharing goods (Lang and Armstrong, 2018), acquiring second-hand fashion products (Cervellon et al., 2012), utilizing them responsibly, repairing to prolong their lifespan, or repurposing for other objectives (Haines and Lee et al., 2021; McNeill et al., 2020; Laitala et al., 2021). Subsequently, expert panels from the fashion industry were engaged in focus groups, and a preliminary assessment involving seven potential consumers was conducted to ascertain the ultimate adjustments aimed at enhancing the validity of the scales. According to the final version of the questionnaire, respondents were asked to indicate the frequency they do such

behaviors from 1 (never) to 5 (always/whenever I have the chance). Data was collected in the first quarter of January 2022. The final sample guaranteed a 95% interval of confidence and a confidence level of 3.5% considering sex, age, level of education, geographical area of targeted population.

3.3 Sample characteristics

The demographic characteristics of the 5,124 individual respondents are detailed in Table 1. The measurement instrument consisted of 30 items, representative of consumers' actions in different product lifecycle stages (Table 2). On the survey, each individual was asked to rate on a 5-point scale their evaluation about how frequently take a specific action (adopts a certain behavior), ranging from "1", being never, to "5" being "always, whenever I get the chance".

Table A1 (Appendix) presents information about mean item scores and standard deviation across countries and in the total sample, and a first scale reliability analysis using Cronbach's α . All α coefficients, calculated by country show an acceptable value (α_{DE} = 0.93; α_{ES} = 0.92; α_{FR} = 0.93; α_{IT} = 0.92; α_{ES} = 0.92; α_{PL} = 0.94).

INSERT TABLE 1 HERE

INSERT TABLE 2 HERE

3.4 Methodology: applying the item response theory (IRT) framework to circular consumer behavior

Item response theory (IRT) is a family of latent trait models first proposed in the field of cognitive psychology for attitude assessment (Lord et al., 1968), under the assumption that many behaviors are driven by processes operating outside of individual awareness (Uhlmann et al., 2012). In recent years, IRT models have become increasingly popular in many disciplines, to estimate indirect (implicit) measures of latent characteristics, such as attitudes, abilities, beliefs, or behavioral characteristics (e.g. purchasing tendency). IRT has been used in economics, for detecting situations of need or deprivation (Szeles and Fusco, 2013), in medicine, to identify complex health conditions (Prenovost et al., 2018), and in strategic management, to capture CSR-related behavior in organizations (Carroll et al., 2016).

Typically, a measurement instrument consisting of a set of items is applied to a sample of subjects, minimizing both the individual awareness of the measurement construct and the ability to control and regulate responses, therefore avoiding social desirability biases (Antons and Piller, 2015).

The IRT framework models the functional relationship between a

respondent's underlying latent trait level and an item-level stimulus, to form an expected probability of the response patterns (Chalmers, 2012:2). Specifically, an IRT model is defined by a mathematical function used to describe the conditional probability of a response to an item (indicative of an action) given the level of one (or more) individual's underlying latent characteristics (Thissen and Steinberg, 1986).

Historically, IRT models have been mostly used in a confirmatory spirit, by modeling the item response probabilities as a function of known underlying latent characteristics of interest. However, IRT can also be applied in an exploratory manner, whereby the number of latent characteristics is not assumed known beforehand, and is instead estimated empirically (and tested by comparing nested models). Hence, adopting an IRT framework is crucial for studies aiming to model patterns of individuals' observable actions to inductively explore and measure unobserved (latent) traits.

In this study, we regard circular consumption attitudes (hereafter, circular attitudes) as a set of unobservable (latent) characteristics that reflect consumers' actions (behavioral patterns) in different stages of circular consumption. As a core concept of social psychology, attitudes constitute learned dispositions (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) that integrate individuals' beliefs, prior experiences, and resulting value structures. These attitudes guide individuals' judgments (Ajzen, 2001), thereby influencing their intentions to behave and subsequent behaviors.

In the context of circular consumption, the object under evaluation is selection of different actions along the product lifecycle including buy, reuse, share, and second-hand practices, use, repair and after use disposal. When confronted with a set of options, individuals with different beliefs, value structures and inclinations will be more or less inclined to pursue different actions based on the value (the benefit) each action offers to them. As attitudes are reflected in the evaluative judgments of key individuals (Ajzen, 2001), diverse observed behavioral patterns will distinguish individuals with different value structures supporting circular attitudes.

The proposed application focuses on the relationship between patterns of observed consumer behaviors (consumers' assessments regarding different actions along the product lifecycle) and its underlying circular attitudes.

We devise a model focusing on the perceived benefit (value) that an individual (a consumer) receives from the decision to take a particular action more or less frequently (or not to take it at all), given the individual's level of one (or more) underlying latent characteristic(s) of interest. As the individual level of the latent characteristic(s) affects the probability of pursuing different types of actions more or less frequently (i.e., the probability of frequently pursuing an action j is influenced by the level of the latent characteristic(s) of an individual i), the IRT-based measure of each latent characteristic is conceived as an indicator reflecting individuals'

evaluations of the costs/benefits of pursuing different actions².

In addition to determining a continuous measure of the latent characteristic(s) of interest, (i.e., each individual's position along the latent traits *continuum*), the IRT model produces estimations of item-level parameters, enabling to evaluate test questions (i.e., to assess of the types of items that better qualify respondents with high and low levels of the underlying latent characteristics) (Van Der Linden and Hambleton, 2013). In this context, the probability that an individual adopts a specific behavioral pattern is conditional upon (i.e., a function of) its unobservable level of the latent characteristic(s) epitomizing circular attitudes. Therefore, it is assumed that each individual's position along the *continuum* of each latent characteristic of interest) will epitomize the level of the individual's attitude resulting from their value structure.

The data input into the model consists of n=5,124 individuals' response patterns of graded scores for the 30 items, measuring the frequency of a set of consumer actions along the lifecycle (Table 3).

We specify an IRT model for graded responses (IRT-GRM) using the graded scores for each item that include four categories k=0; k=1; k=2; k=3³.

Table 3 reports the frequency of item responses in the sample.

INSERT TABLE 3 HERE

Under the IRT framework, the individual's subjective evaluation of taking different actions with higher or lower frequency is conditional on the level of the individual's latent characteristic(s) of interest. The IRT-GRM is therefore specified for the probability that a response of category k or higher will be observed (Samejima, 1969).

Specifically, the probability that an individual i will provide a response corresponding to the k^{th} category of item j (π_{ijk}) (i.e., the probability that the i^{th} individual will take a j^{th} action more or less frequently) is computed as the probability of observing a response above the lower boundary of the category ($\pi *_{ij,k}$) minus the probability of observing a response above the upper boundary of the category ($\pi *_{ij,k+1}$):

² Such an exploratory analysis of circular behavior in terms of the underlying decision process is strongly consistent with extant research examining the determinants of consumer behavior through the use of reflective measures (see, e.g. Sudbury-Rielly and Kohlbacher, 2016).

³ To be input in the IRT graded response model, the item responses were re-codified in a 4-points ordinal scale, "0" being "I never or rarely took this action", and "1"- "2"- "3" being "sometimes", "often", and "always, whenever I get the chance", respectively.

$$\pi_{ij,k} = P(Y_{ij} = k | \theta_i) = \pi_{ij,k} - \pi_{ij,k+1} \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_i \sim N(0,1)$$

Where:

$$\pi_{ij,1} = 1, \quad \pi_{ij,k+1} = 0$$

$$P(Y_{ij} \leq k | \theta_i) = \frac{\exp(\alpha_j \theta_{i-k_{j,k}})}{1 + \exp(\alpha_j \theta_{i-k_{j,k}})} \quad (2)$$

We adopt an exploratory approach, whereby no prior knowledge of the latent structure (the relationship between items and latent characteristics) is included in the model, and the number of dimensions is not assumed known beforehand. The dimensionality of the latent characteristic(s) is instead estimated empirically by comparing nested models (Bock and Aitkin 1981). To this aim, we use a multidimensional item response theory (MIRT) approach, where latent characteristics are allowed to correlate⁴.

The multidimensional formalization of IRT models for graded responses (MIRT-GRM) is developed as an extension of the unidimensional version, where the response pattern for an individual i to j items (Z_{ij}) is an underlying unobservable variable that is manifested in a vector of observed ordered item responses $Y_i = (Y_{i1}; Y_{i2}; \dots; Y_{in})$. MIRT-GRM models Z_{ij} as a linear combination of a vector of m individual-level latent traits $\theta_i = (\theta_{1i}; \theta_{2i}; \dots; \theta_{mi})$, and a vector of v item-level parameters $\alpha_j = (\alpha_{j1}; \alpha_{j2}; \dots; \alpha_{jv})$:

$$Z_{ij} = \alpha_{j1} \theta_{j1} + \alpha_{j2} \theta_{j2} + \dots + \alpha_{jv} \theta_{jm} + \varepsilon_{ij} = \alpha'_j \theta_j + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Where ε_{ij} is an unobserved random variable that is assumed to be distributed as $N(0, \sigma_j^2)$.

The output of the model consists of three types of estimates.

1) *Individual-level estimates.* At the individual level, θ_i is the vector of latent characteristics of interest estimated as continuous measures. The IRT model assumes that the higher the level of each latent characteristic

⁴ MIRT is a methodology that has been developed with the principal aim of dealing with the situation of complexity in psychological measurement when several latent characteristics influence the individual's response on each item (Reckase, 1997). By introducing a person trait and item discrimination parameters for each latent characteristic measured by a test item, MIRT models permit separate inferences with reference to each distinct latent dimension of an individual (Ackerman, 1994).

for an individual i (θ_i) is, the higher the probability that the individual i will pursue a given pattern of behavior more frequently as well.

2) *Item-level estimates: discrimination parameters.* At the item level, the vector of discrimination parameters α_j for each action j , conditional to the underlying level of the latent characteristic (θ_i) informs about each item's properties within the construct. If α_j is positive, then individuals with higher levels of the latent characteristic(s) are more likely to take the action j ; if α_j is negative, then individuals with higher levels of the latent characteristic(s) are less likely to take the action j . Thus, discrimination parameters α_j allow us to assess if and how much each item in the proposed scale (each type of consumer's action) can discriminate individuals with higher levels of θ_i from individuals with lower levels of θ_i , thus revealing the strength of each item in explaining each latent characteristic. In the context of this study, IRT discrimination parameters allow us to assess how different sets of consumer actions 'map' onto one or more latent characteristic(s) of interest and their comparative relevance in discriminating consumers with different levels of the latent characteristic(s) in different lifecycle stages.

3) *Item-level estimates: thresholds.* A second set of item-level estimates, threshold parameters (k_{jk}), are associated with the k^{th} category of each item, j , and model the unobservable response process Z_{ij} according to the psychological mechanism under study. Such parameters represent the likelihood that an individual will take a particular action conditional upon its level of θ_i . In our model, and for each item, this probability k is estimated according to three thresholds: $k_{(0-1)} < k_{(1-2)} < k_{(2-3)}$. As k_{jk} increases, all individuals are more likely to take the specific action frequently, while as k_{jk} decreases, only individuals with a particular level of the latent characteristic(s) will take the specific action frequently. Thus, threshold parameters inform about the position of each item along with the measures of the latent traits.

The simultaneous estimation of individual-level measures of the latent characteristic(s), and item-level parameters allows to investigate the relationship between specific patterns of observed behaviors and differences among individuals along the attitude(s) continuum. Thus, discrimination and threshold parameters enable the researcher to assess the content validity of the test questions (i.e., to assess the types of behaviors that better qualify respondents with high and low levels of the underlying characteristics of interest within the proposed scale) (Van Der Linden and Hambleton, 2013) Further, the possibility to relate individual-level characteristics (θ_i), to item-level characteristics (α_j and k_{ij}) enables the researcher to develop a nuanced, theory-based interpretation of the latent constructs.

4. Results

The *mirt* package in the R environment (Chalmers, 2012) was used

for estimating MIRT-GRM parameters for our exploratory model by using maximum-likelihood methods. The model employs an expectation–maximization (EM) algorithm, using the Gauss-Hermite quadrature as an iterative method to find (local) maximum likelihood or maximum *a posteriori* estimates of parameters as the model depends on unobserved latent variables (Bock and Aitkin 1981; Cai, 2010).

To assess the dimensionality of the latent constructs we adopted an iterative approach by running MIRT-GRM models with progressively one, two, and three exploratory dimensions, and checked the improvements of goodness of fit statistics for nested models (Tables 4-5). The model fit statistics validated the assumption of multidimensionality of the construct (circular attitudes), suggesting a three-dimensional model be a good fit.

INSERT TABLE 4 HERE

The choice was based on the significant improvements observed in the AIC and BIC statistics for the three-dimensional model compared to the two-dimensional and the unidimensional (confirmatory) ones, with smaller values representing better fit (Hu and Bentler, 1995).

INSERT TABLE 5 HERE

Further, the goodness of fit statistics confirmed that the values of the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) -used to assess the goodness of approximation and for model selection and the Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual (SRMSR) statistic for the three-dimensional model fell beyond the cut-off threshold developed by Maydeu-Olivares and Joe (2014), indicating close fit ($RMSEA < 0.05$) and adequate fit ($SRMSR < 0.05$) of the three-dimensional model. Finally, the lower value of the limited information test statistic (M2 statistic) by Maydeu-Olivares and Joe, (2006), confirmed a better approximation of the three-dimensional model up to any level of association of the discrete variables (RMSEA2).

INSERT TABLE 6 HERE

Table 6 reports the estimates of item-level discrimination parameters (α_{jv}), the thresholds (k_{jk}), and their relation with the three latent dimensions (where $v=1$ on θ_1 , $v=2$ on θ_2 , and $v=3$ on θ_3). Particularly, the capability of an action j to differentiate individuals with different levels of θ_1 , θ_2 or θ_3 increases as the value of the discrimination parameters (α_{jv}) increases.

4.1. Environmental-centric circular attitude

The first set of items shows the highest values of item discrimination parameters with respect to θ_3 (α_{j3}). The interpretation of the latent characteristic derives from the meaning of this relevant set of items. More in detail, the analysis of item-level discrimination parameters allows to assess the “informative power” of each item in discriminating individuals with higher levels of θ_3 from those with lower levels of θ_3 , and therefore the types of actions that qualify θ_3 .

Individuals with higher levels of θ_3 are consumers inclined to a) choose garments that have a low environmental impact during production ($\hat{\alpha}_{I6,3} = 2.853$), b) choose garments with labels that demonstrate the ethical behavior of the manufacturer ($\hat{\alpha}_{I8,3} = 2.472$); c) buy garments made with little use of water ($\hat{\alpha}_{I2,3} = 2.469$), d) prefer garments made from fibers produced through low environmental impact methods ($\hat{\alpha}_{I3,3} = 2.370$) or made from recycled materials ($\hat{\alpha}_{I4,3} = 2.059$) and that d) avoid buying garments made in countries where there are working conditions close to exploitation ($\hat{\alpha}_{I9,3} = 2.019$). As these consumers’ actions are the most informative items for θ_3 , we interpret θ_3 as an attitude derived by individual value structures that assign high importance (value) to the environmental impact of consumption.

Our findings also show that the set of actions distinguishing individuals with high levels of θ_3 is primarily associated with the purchasing stage. This attitude becomes manifest in observed patterns of rational consumption choices, oriented toward gathering information on the production process, raw materials, and use of environmental resources. In other words, individuals with high levels of θ_3 represent a “social circle” guided by a strong set of values and beliefs emphasizing the importance of safeguarding the natural environment through the selection of products with lower environmental impact in the purchasing stage. This contention is reinforced by the high discriminating power of I11, I12 and I7 on θ_3 (consumers with high levels of θ_3 buy clothes with sustainable packaging, made of reused materials and locally produced). Thus, θ_3 represents individuals’ environment-centric circular attitude (θ_{ENV}).

4.2. Social-centric circular attitude

A second set of items show the highest discrimination power among individuals with respect to θ_1 (α_{j1}). Individuals with a high level of θ_1 are consumers inclined to a) rent clothes instead of buying them ($\hat{\alpha}_{I14,1} =$

2.866); b) buy original vintage clothing ($\hat{\alpha}_{117,1} = 2.037$), and/or second-hand modern clothing ($\hat{\alpha}_{116,1} = 1.627$), c) eager to exchange clothes with other people ($\hat{\alpha}_{115,1} = 1.958$), d) to customize/repair clothes ($\hat{\alpha}_{130,1} = 1.989$), e) to sell them for other clothes ($\hat{\alpha}_{127,1} = 1.748$) and/or f) to plot used clothing items to family members or relatives ($\hat{\alpha}_{128,1} = 1.435$).

Thus, θ_I represents a latent attitude that becomes manifest in consumer actions related to renting, reusing (rather than buying new items), repairing/customizing clothes, and sharing and/or exchanging them, across different stages of the lifecycle (from purchasing to after use-disposal). This attitude becomes manifested in observed patterns of social behavior, as individuals with high levels of θ_I view consumption not as an individual pursuit, but as a social process. We conclude that θ_I characterizes “social circles” of consumers giving relevance to the social dimension of circular behavior, focusing to keep the product’s value into the socio-economic system. Accordingly, we conceptualize, θ_I as a social-centric circular attitude (θ_{soc}) seemingly characterizing customer segments aligned with to the new business models emerging in the circular economy paradigm (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019).

4.3. Resources-centric circular attitude

A third set of items show the highest discrimination power among individuals with respect to θ_2 (α_{j2}). This behavioral pattern qualifies consumers who highly value the economic benefits of circular behavior, in terms of preserving resources or reducing waste. In this case, nearly all items in the use stage carry significant importance in discriminating individuals with higher levels of θ_2 from those with lower levels of θ_2 . These individuals tend to a) wash clothes at low temperatures ($\hat{\alpha}_{19,2} = 1.648$), b) avoid using dryer or ironing clothing, when possible ($\hat{\alpha}_{122,2} = 1.467$), c) pay attention to the directions on garment labels that state how to wash the garments ($\hat{\alpha}_{121,2} = 1.395$), d) wash clothes with mild or natural detergents ($\hat{\alpha}_{120,2} = 1.271$) and/or try to reduce the number of washes ($\hat{\alpha}_{118,2} = 1.195$). These relevant actions reflect a latent -attitude indicating “social circles” of individuals characterized by value structures where environmental benefits align with economic considerations, thus embodying a resources-centric circular attitude (θ_{RES}). These individuals are guided by a set of values and attitudes giving equal importance to economic and environmental considerations, and consequently tend to adopt eco-efficient behaviors. Figure 1 offers a visual representation of this.

INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE

The second set of item-level parameters (thresholds, k_{jk}) is estimated based on individuals' responses to the 30 items. By following an exploratory approach, our model does not assume which of the item responses is related to each of the three latent constructs (i.e. it has no *a priori* knowledge of the latent structure). Item-level thresholds can reflect the “criticality level” of each specific consumer action. Higher levels of “criticality” (higher values of the threshold parameters) correspond to lower probabilities to observe responses in higher categories (lower probabilities that an action j is taken frequently). This means that actions characterized by higher values of the threshold parameters are taken by more individuals in lower frequency and are, therefore, less “critical”. As for the MIRT-GRM model, it is not possible to unambiguously order the items by the response probability based on the threshold parameters (Martelli, 2014) we fix $\hat{\theta}_1$, $\hat{\theta}_2$ and $\hat{\theta}_3$ at the mean value of 0, and use threshold parameters to compare the probabilities of observing a response in each category of an item.

The results show that an individual with an average value of circular attitudes ($\hat{\theta}_1=0$, $\hat{\theta}_2=0$ and $\hat{\theta}_3=0$) is more likely to engage in frequent actions related to reusing, sharing and repairing clothes, to buy clothes made from recycled materials or made with little use of water rather (i.e. higher social-centric attitudes) than, for instance, taking frequent actions related to “sustainable use”, such as washing clothes at low temperatures or reducing the number of washing (i.e. resources-centric attitudes), as such actions will probably be also taken by individuals with lower-than-average levels of the latent characteristics. Interestingly, as shown in Table 6, the values of the thresholds $k_{(1-2)}$ and $k_{(2-3)}$ for items related to reuse (I12-I13), share (I14, I15), second hand practices (I16, I17) and those related to purchase of garments made with little use of water (I2) or from recycled materials (I4) are regularly lower than those for items related to consumer choices related to purchase stage (I1, I3, I5, I10) and the use stage (I18-I22) which are supported by a higher availability of information (e.g. labels or QR codes).

This implies that, for individuals with average circular attitudes, environmental and social-centric attitudes, which become manifest in renting, exchanging clothes in the stage of purchase and product disposal, and in recycling, reusing, sharing, and repairing clothes in the stage of after-use are more relevant than resource-centric attitudes, translating into actions involving a responsible use of resources.

The ex-post estimated correlation among the three latent characteristics is consistent with the described results (Table 7).

INSERT TABLE 7 HERE

The value of the correlation coefficient between θ_{SOC} and θ_{ENV} is high ($\hat{r}_{\text{SOC,ENV}} = 0.574$), while the coefficient is relatively lower considering θ_{RES} and θ_{ENV} ($\hat{r}_{\text{RES,ENV}} = 0.357$), and significantly lower between θ_{SOC} and θ_{RES} ($\hat{r}_{\text{SOC,RES}} = 0.054$). The value of $\hat{r}_{\text{SOC,ENV}}$ indicates that individual attitudes resulting from a strong and positive evaluation of the environmental aspects of consumption is positively and consistently associated with value structures prioritizing the social aspects of consumption. Thus, environment-centric attitudes and social-centric attitudes better reflect patterns of consumers' actions that extend from the purchase stage to recycling, reusing, sharing, repairing, and, in general, to after use disposal (circular attitudes), compared to resources-centric attitudes. A lower, but still significant association is observed between the environment-centric attitudes and resources-centric attitudes. Individuals with high levels of such attitudes will frequently take action in the phases of purchase and use of the products. Finally, the association between resources-centric attitudes and social-centric attitudes is positive but weak, indicating that the coexistence of the two attitudes is not diffused across individuals. This is also confirmed by the different patterns of actions that such attitudes reflect (buy vs. recycle, reuse, sharing, repairing, and after-use disposal).

The results are confirmed by the reliability test conducted check the internal and external validity of the proposed constructs⁵ (See Appendix B for details).

5. Discussion

This study undertook an inductive exploration of the latent attitudes underlying observed patterns of circular consumer behavior to uncover circular attitudes. To this aim, the study focused on behaviors of expanded scope, specifically those incorporating a lifecycle logic that is typical of the circular economy paradigm, namely, the circular consumption.

In this context, our exploratory application of the IRT framework to develop implicit, reflective measures of consumers' latent attitudes allowed to devise a model focusing the perceived benefits (value) that a consumer derives from choosing a specific action along different stages of the lifecycle. The IRT approach models the decision-making process (i.e. observed patterns of item responses) as the reflection of individuals' latent level of one

⁵ The specification of the exploratory MIRT model follows many of the rules in the structural equation modelling (SEM) framework for exploratory FA. However, one important assumption of IRT models is that item responses are independent (uncorrelated) given a persons' level of a latent characteristic; it means that any existing correlation between observed responses to different items are absorbed by the latent construct. Thus, compared to other techniques based on classical test theory (as, for instance, Cronbach alpha's test), IRT measures show higher reliability. Each construct's internal validity is assessed conditional on the scores of the estimated latent construct. For the same reasons, the use of MIRT yields also much reliable parameter estimates in small samples.

or more characteristics of interest (attitudes). These characteristics epitomize reflective measures of circular attitudes.

In the proposed application, the probability of an individual adopting a set of actions is contingent upon (i.e., a function of) the unobservable level of the latent characteristic(s). Thus, we assume that each individual's position along the continuum (i.e., the individual level of the latent characteristic(s)) epitomizes the individual's value structure. In other words, as consumers adopt any of these behaviors throughout the product lifecycle, each is sparked by different (and sometimes recurring) latent circular attitudes that lurk backstage.

Our findings indicate that, in line with the circular economy paradigm, consumers' circular attitude should be conceptualized as a complex and multidimensional construct. The model estimates three individual-level measures of latent characteristics (θ_i), encompassing three latent dimensions that symbolize distinct attitudes and resultant value structures: social-centric circular attitudes (θ_{SOC}), resources-centric circular attitudes (θ_{REC}), and environmental-centric circular attitudes (θ_{ENV}). The item-level estimates (discrimination parameters) for the three latent constructs reveals that these attitudes reflect different behavioral patterns across the product lifecycle.

Individuals with a high level of social-centric attitudes tend to extend their consumption actions along the product lifecycle. These individuals are less inclined to purchase new clothes and more inclined to rent clothes, buy original vintage clothes, or second-hand clothes. Additionally, they show a greater propensity to engage in activities such as sharing, customizing/repairing, donating, selling or exchanging, and reusing. These attitudes significantly shape behavior, particularly in the sharing and second-hand phases, as well as in the repair and after-use stages.

In contrast, individuals with a high level of resources-centric circular attitudes predominantly put their values into action in the use phase of the garment, focusing on actions that aim to preserve the garment's durability. In this context, the attitude and corresponding value structure are aligned with the goal of extending the lifespan of clothes to maximize their duration, with a low consumption of resources. These consumers are less inclined to purchase sustainable clothes but are more inclined to adopt practices that contribute to preserving the longevity of their existing wardrobe.

Lastly, individuals with higher environment-centric attitudes are more inclined to purchase sustainable clothes. They pay close attention to information regarding environmental impact, production location, and extend this consideration to packaging. It is noteworthy that the decision to embrace sustainable actions corresponds to choices that are often more challenging to implement.

Our study offers several contributions to the current academic discourse. Firstly, it extends recent research on circular purchasing behaviors, which traditionally relies on rational predictive models like TRA or TPB theory (Abbasi et al., 2022; Rausch and Kopplin, 2021). We do this

by emphasizing the role of various attitudes in shaping such behaviors. Moving beyond a reductionist approach that predominantly considers environmental- attitudes and beliefs (Bigliardi et al., 2022; Tan et al., 2022), we highlight the existence of diverse and sometimes divergent attitudes influencing the adoption of different circular behaviors. Environmental, resources, and social-centric attitudes represent three sets of values and beliefs that could introduce tensions into the purchasing decision-making process, hindering the widespread adoption of a comprehensive circular behavior without the development of a flexible and paradoxical mindset in consumers (Miron-Spektor et al., 2018; Testa et al., 2022; Koide et al., 2023).

Secondly, the study underscores the broad scope of circular consumer behaviors, extending beyond the purchase decision to encompass various stages of the product life cycle, including use and post-use phases (Di Iorio et al., 2023). The paradigm of the circular economy has expanded the spectrum of behaviors individuals can adopt to contribute to a circular transition. Focusing solely on individual behaviors such as purchasing recycled (Pretner et al., 2021), refurbished (Bigliardi et al., 2022), or eco-efficient (Ng et al., 2023) products, as well as second-hand items (Rausch and Kopplin, 2021), limits the understanding of a phenomenon that is much more intricate and can manifest in various behavioral forms.

Additionally, the article contributes to the ongoing debate on developing more comprehensive measurements capable of capturing the diverse behaviors that consumers may adopt. Sudbury-Riley and Kohlbacker (2016) and Hosta and Zabkar (2020) introduced novel scales primarily emphasizing actual behavior and sustainable considerations, respectively. More recently, Di Iorio and colleagues (2023) made advancements by capturing holistic consumer actions throughout a product's life but missed addressing the role of emerging consumption models such as sharing, reuse, or second-hand. While our study did not aim to develop a new scale and, therefore, did not follow the rigorous steps required for creating a valid measurement scale (Hinkin, 1995), our use of the IRT method provides valuable insights for future research focused on developing a comprehensive and holistic measurement scale capable of capturing the multidimensional nature of circular consumer behavior.

The results yield implications for both managerial decision-makers and policymakers. Managers need to be attuned to potential tensions that consumers may encounter throughout their decision-making and purchasing processes. Marketing campaigns should strategically consider these potential divergences, aiming to inspire consumers to identify solutions for addressing them. Furthermore, adopting a life cycle perspective is crucial when analyzing consumers' experiences. Addressing multiple needs across the various stages of consumer experience, from the decision-making phase to post-product use, is essential for maximizing satisfaction. By designing products that cater to a broad spectrum of these needs, companies can not only enhance competitiveness but also contribute to the circular transition of their products.

Policymakers could derive valuable insights from the research. Strengthening the role of consumers in the circular transition presents policymakers with ambitious and intricate challenges. Recognizing the diverse attitudes which nurture consumers decisions throughout a product's lifecycle should inspire policymakers to devise tools that assist consumers in navigating tensions and weighing different alternatives. A promising avenue for regulation involves how environmental information is integrated with products in the marketplace. Defining rules on how environmental information must be disclosure may help consumers to be aware of potential conflicts related to their own attitudes and, encourage them to seek compromises. The European Commission's initiatives on eco-design for sustainable products and substantiating green claim is a positive step forward. Specifically, the proposal for a mandatory environmental label encompassing various sustainability dimensions tailored to specific product categories as well as the definition of clear and unambiguous role on how to formulate green claim aims to elucidate the intricacies of circular paradigm for consumers. Moreover, the insistence on providing robust environmental information grounded in recognized methodologies such as life cycle assessment mitigates the risk of making misleading decisions.

Several insights for future research emerge from our study. First, since three main behavioral attitudes emerge, scholars should work for developing new scale able to capture the diverse manifestation of the three attitudes taking into account their emotional and cognitive components according to the tri-component ABC model of attitudes (Breckler, 1984). Second, researcher could analyse profoundly the potential tensions experienced by a consumer in choosing among different circular alternatives. Experimental research may be designed for identifying how the potentially competing attitudes are addressed by consumers and which creative solution is stimulated by the awareness of such tensions.

5. Concluding remarks

Drawing on the theoretical foundations of attitudes, this study explored a wide set of observed heterogeneous consumers' actions across the product lifecycle to underline three different types of attitudes (and related value structures) influencing individuals' decision processes underlying circular consumption: social-centric, resources-centric and environmental-centric circular attitudes.

The study adds to prior research on consumers' attitudes in circular economy – mostly drawing on scales measuring consumers' future intentions or beliefs- by adopting an inductive perspective and a reflective measurement approach, allowing to explicitly be focusing on the attitude-behavior link in circular consumption through the use of IRT models.

Compared to prior research, mostly focused on specific consumers' actions (e.g. in the purchase phase, and/or in the use phase concerning recycling) and on environmental-centric consumers' attitudes, this study

advances current knowledge of the multidimensional nature of the circular paradigm, as it involves a wider spectrum of consumers' decisions, and offers several alternatives to contribute to the efficient utilization of resources across the product lifecycle.

Our findings emphasize the relevance of resource-centric and social-centric consumer attitudes beyond environmental-centric attitudes in influencing distinct patterns of circular consumer behavior, and underlines the types of behaviors pursued by consumers with different (and partially overlapping) value structures. Further, our findings suggest that environmental-centric and resources-centric consumer attitudes may be enhanced by the availability of information on products' labels or QR codes (concerning, e.g. the production process and the use of the product), social centric circular attitudes reflect consumer behaviors in line with the value proposition of recent circular business models, where the focus is on maintaining the product's value into the socio-economic system.

As the consumer is a central actor in the emerging circular economy paradigm, and attitudes represent time-consistent learned dispositions influencing consumers' evaluation along the entire product lifecycle, our findings might constitute the basis to provide targeted information to different types of customers, and in different stages of the lifecycle. Further, as individuals with similar attitudes and value structure represent "social circles", our evidence can be useful to team building or to targeted marketing campaigns.

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Tables

TABLE 1 – Sample Characteristics

		IT	DE	ES	FR	PL	Total
	N	1,053	1,018	1,016	1,012	1,025	5,124
Gender [%]	F	50.3	49.4	50.2	50.8	50.7	50.3
	M	49.7	50.6	49.8	49.2	49.3	49.7
Age group [%]	18-24	10.2	10.7	10.5	12.6	10.2	10.9
	25-34	16.0	19.1	16.6	17.9	20.0	17.9
	35-44	19.8	17.3	22.2	19.0	22.6	20.2
	45-54	23.7	20.9	22.7	20.5	17.8	21.1
	55-70	30.3	32.0	27.9	30.0	29.4	29.9
Income class [%]	very low	2.7	2.9	1.7	5.8	1.3	2.9
	low	7.1	6.0	3.9	14.7	4.5	7.2
	medium-low	22.6	20.5	22.0	17.4	20.8	20.7
	medium	50.9	38.3	51.9	35.3	47.1	44.8
	medium-high	13.5	22.2	16.0	18.8	17.0	17.5
	high	0.9	5.2	2.6	5.2	4.8	3.7
	very high	0.8	2.8	1.0	1.4	3.5	1.9
	N/A	1.6	2.1	0.9	1.4	1.1	1.4
N. family members	1	12.0	30.3	13.2	22.5	11.0	17.7
	2	24.0	35.3	29.5	34.7	28.1	30.3
	3	31.8	18.3	31.2	20.4	29.3	26.2
	4	21.7	9.9	19.5	14.1	18.5	16.8
	5+	10.4	6.3	6.6	8.3	13.1	9.0
Civil state [%]	Single	30.0	36.4	26.6	30.9	24.2	29.6
	Involved (not co-habiting)	10.5	8.2	6.8	7.1	10.1	8.6
	Involved (co-habiting)	15.8	13.2	16.4	13.0	25.6	16.8
	Married (not co-habiting)	8.2	12.0	8.2	8.4	6.9	8.7
	Married (co-habiting)	35.5	30.3	42.0	40.5	33.2	36.3
Town size [% residents]	< 10.000	17.5	20.9	13.6	39.0	16.2	21.4
	10.000-30.000	23.2	19.1	16.5	19.9	16.7	19.1
	30.000-100.000	26.1	21.3	17.7	17.6	21.3	20.8
	100.000-250.000	11.2	13.7	17.3	11.6	15.1	13.8
	250.000-500.000	6.5	7.7	11.9	3.6	12.3	8.4
	> 500.000	15.6	17.4	22.9	8.4	18.4	16.5

TABLE 2 - Scale items

ITEM	Description
I1	I choose the highest quality clothes available and durable over time
I2	I buy garments made with little use of water
I3	I prefer buying clothes made from fibers produced through low environmental impact methods
I4	I buy clothes made from recycled materials
I5	I prefer buying clothes made from natural fibers
I6	I choose garments that have a low environmental impact during production
I7	I buy locally (nationally) produced clothing
I8	I choose garments with labels that demonstrate the ethical behavior of the manufacturer
I9	I avoid buying garments made in countries where there are working conditions close to exploitation
I10	I buy clothes without packaging
I11	I buy clothes with sustainable packaging
I12	I buy clothes made of reused materials
I13	When I am tired of my old clothes, I adapt them to create new ones
I14	I happen to rent clothes instead of buying them
I15	I happen to exchange my clothes with other people
I16	I buy second-hand modern clothing
I17	I buy original vintage clothing
I18	I try to reduce the number of washes of garments
I19	I wash clothing at low temperatures
I20	I wash clothes with a mild and/or natural detergent
I21	I pay attention to the directions on garment labels that state how to wash them
I22	I avoid using the dryer and/or ironing clothing whenever possible
I23	I repair/ mend my clothing items.
I24	I ask my family members and/or friends to help me repair my clothing items
I25	I go to a seamstress or the store where I bought the garments
I26	I donate my used clothing items to thrift stores or charity
I27	I sell my used clothing items to thrift stores or exchange them for other clothes
I28	I plot my used clothing items to family members/relatives
I29	I reuse my clothing items for other purposes or turn them into something new
I30	I modify/customize or repair my clothing items

TABLE 3 – Frequency of item responses (n=5,124)

ITEM	1	2	3	4	5	
I1	135	460	1613	1828	1088	5124
I2	552	1040	1875	1104	553	5124
I3	185	583	1791	1682	883	5124
I4	372	975	2093	1173	511	5124
I5	113	394	1434	1921	1262	5124
I6	250	758	2022	1448	646	5124
I7	151	667	1985	1615	706	5124
I8	420	886	1876	1293	649	5124
I9	281	722	1706	1442	973	5124
I10	172	445	1426	1829	1252	5124
I11	241	635	1804	1515	929	5124
I12	581	1018	2102	1005	418	5124
I13	1042	980	1610	1015	477	5124
I14	2840	770	788	486	240	5124
I15	1531	895	1373	917	408	5124
I16	1271	874	1511	1026	442	5124
I17	2064	1066	1165	570	259	5124
I18	272	585	1647	1575	1045	5124
I19	100	317	1314	1809	1584	5124
I20	217	477	1478	1685	1267	5124
I21	172	450	1258	1533	1711	5124
I22	237	508	1178	1361	1840	5124
I23	695	827	1534	1182	886	5124
I24	943	775	1568	1126	712	5124
I25	923	882	1566	1094	659	5124
I26	581	626	1512	1427	978	5124
I27	1595	898	1325	843	463	5124
I28	543	747	1801	1313	720	5124
I29	369	695	1857	1372	831	5124
I30	786	963	1710	1045	620	5124

TABLE 4 – Dimensionality test: alternative models fit

Model	Log-likelihood	N. est. parameters	AIC	BIC	AIC diff.	BIC diff.
Three-dimensional	-168,809.5	177	337,973.0	339,130.9	-4,246.6	-4,063.4
Two-dimensional	-170,960.8	149	342,219.6	343,194.3	-9,365.6	-9,175.9
Unidimensional	-175,672.6	120	351,585.2	352,370.2	-	-

TABLE 5 – Goodness of fit statistics

Model	M2	df	p	RMSEA	SRMSR	TLI	CFI
Three-dimensional	2136.929	288	0.000	0.035	0.032	0.978	0.983
Two-dimensional	5578.546	316	0.000	0.057	0.051	0.942	0.951
Unidimensional	5629.310	345	0.000	0.055	0.085	0.947	0.951

TABLE 6 – Results of the MIRT-GRM model

		DISCRIMINATION (α_{jv})			THRESHOLDS (k_{jk})		
		$\hat{\alpha}_{j^1}$	$\hat{\alpha}_{j^2}$	$\hat{\alpha}_{j^3}$	$\hat{k}_{j(0-1)}$	$\hat{k}_{j(1-2)}$	$\hat{k}_{j(2-3)}$
I1	I choose the highest quality clothes available and durable over time	-0.096	0.426	1.305	2.612	0.373	-1.774
I2	I buy garments made with little use of water	0.266	-0.385	2.469	1.452	-1.284	-3.741
I3	I prefer buying clothes made from fibers produced through low environmental impact methods	-0.112	0.297	2.370	2.941	0.033	-2.747
I4	I buy clothes made from recycled materials	0.646	-0.34	2.059	1.809	-1.211	-3.775
I5	I prefer buying clothes made from natural fibers	-0.373	0.676	1.319	2.901	0.685	-1.551
I6	I choose garments that have a low environmental impact during production	0.025	-0.11	2.853	2.684	-0.665	-3.735
I7	I buy locally (nationally) produced clothing	0.013	0.172	1.616	2.326	-0.236	-2.608
I8	I choose garments with labels that demonstrate the ethical behavior of the manufacturer	0.219	-0.165	2.472	1.939	-0.868	-3.478
I9	I avoid buying garments made in countries where there are working conditions close to exploitation	-0.134	0.259	2.019	2.211	-0.137	-2.296
I10	I buy clothes without packaging	0.029	0.603	0.748	2.357	0.504	-1.393
I11	I buy clothes with sustainable packaging	0.019	0.316	1.741	2.333	-0.112	-2.276
I12	I buy clothes made of reused materials	1.160	-0.137	1.458	1.378	-1.573	-4.012
I13	When I am tired of my old clothes I adapt them to create new ones	1.504	0.209	0.577	0.682	-1.365	-3.434
I14	I happen to rent clothes instead of buying them	2.866	-1.221	0.501	-2.076	-3.926	-6.081
I15	I happen to exchange my clothes with other people	1.958	0.055	0.123	0.166	-1.695	-3.786
I16	I buy second-hand modern clothing	1.627	-0.081	0.118	0.457	-1.362	-3.328
I17	I buy original vintage clothing	2.037	-0.614	0.288	-0.811	-2.749	-4.649
I18	I try to reduce the number of washes of garments	0.401	1.195	0.300	2.150	0.121	-1.815
I19	I wash clothing at low temperatures	-0.022	1.648	0.255	3.409	1.022	-1.206

I20	I wash clothes with a mild and/or natural detergent	0.144	1.271	0.866	2.700	0.517	-1.661
I21	I pay attention to the directions on garment labels that state how to wash them	-0.241	1.395	0.684	2.813	0.850	-1.003
I22	I avoid using the dryer and/or ironing clothing whenever possible	0.081	1.467	0.051	2.414	0.759	-0.788
I23	I repair/ mend my clothing items.	1.191	0.774	-0.098	1.166	-0.489	-2.055
I24	I ask my family members and/or friends to help me repair my clothing items	1.097	0.459	0.007	0.880	-0.715	-2.275
I25	I go to a seamstress or the store where I bought the garments	0.707	0.258	0.458	0.763	-0.780	-2.317
I26	I donate my used clothing items to thrift stores or charity	0.677	0.538	0.339	1.431	-0.150	-1.770
I27	I sell my used clothing items to thrift stores or exchange them for other clothes	1.748	-0.073	-0.027	0.071	-1.590	-3.286
I28	I plot my used clothing items to family members/relatives	1.435	0.572	-0.009	1.522	-0.563	-2.497
I29	I reuse my clothing items for other purposes or turn them into something new	0.970	0.874	0.109	1.772	-0.334	-2.159
I30	I modify/customize or repair my clothing items	1.989	0.763	-0.097	1.103	-1.157	-3.154

v=1 for the j items on θ_1 , v=2 for the j items on θ_2 and v=3 for the j items on θ_3

TABLE 7 - Correlation matrix.

	θ_{SOC}	θ_{RES}	θ_{ENV}
θ_{SOC}	1		
θ_{RES}	0.054	1	
θ_{ENV}	0.574	0.357	1

Figure legends

FIGURE 1 - Circular consumption items and corresponding latent attitudes

A Appendix

TABLE A1: Mean item scores by country

	DE		ES		FR		IT		PL	
	Mean	SD								
I1	3.3	1.0	3.9	0.9	3.6	1.0	3.7	0.9	3.7	0.9
I2	2.9	1.1	3.1	1.1	2.8	1.2	3.1	1.2	3.2	1.1
I3	3.3	1.1	3.6	1.0	3.4	1.1	3.5	1.0	3.6	1.0
I4	2.9	1.0	3.2	1.0	3.0	1.0	3.1	1.1	3.3	1.0
I5	3.6	1.1	3.8	0.9	3.6	1.0	3.9	0.9	3.9	1.0
I6	3.2	1.0	3.4	1.0	3.1	1.0	3.4	1.0	3.4	1.0
I7	3.2	1.0	3.5	0.9	3.2	1.1	3.6	0.9	3.5	0.9
I8	3.0	1.1	3.3	1.1	3.0	1.1	3.4	1.1	3.2	1.1
I9	3.3	1.1	3.5	1.1	3.4	1.1	3.5	1.1	3.4	1.1
I10	3.8	1.1	3.7	1.0	3.6	1.0	3.7	1.0	3.7	1.0
I11	3.4	1.1	3.5	1.1	3.4	1.1	3.5	1.0	3.5	1.1
I12	2.8	1.1	3.0	1.1	2.8	1.1	2.9	1.1	3.1	1.1
I13	2.3	1.2	3.1	1.2	2.6	1.3	2.9	1.2	3.1	1.1
I14	1.7	1.1	2.0	1.2	1.9	1.2	1.9	1.3	2.2	1.3
I15	2.2	1.3	2.7	1.3	2.5	1.3	2.6	1.3	2.8	1.2
I16	2.6	1.3	2.6	1.3	2.7	1.3	2.5	1.3	3.2	1.2
I17	2.0	1.1	2.2	1.2	2.2	1.2	2.2	1.3	2.4	1.2
I18	3.4	1.1	3.7	1.1	3.3	1.2	3.6	1.0	3.5	1.1
I19	3.8	1.0	3.9	1.0	3.9	1.0	3.9	0.9	3.8	0.9
I20	3.5	1.1	3.8	1.0	3.4	1.2	3.8	1.0	3.7	1.0
I21	3.7	1.2	3.8	1.1	3.8	1.2	3.9	1.0	3.8	1.1
I22	3.8	1.2	3.8	1.1	3.8	1.2	3.8	1.1	3.7	1.1
I23	2.9	1.3	3.3	1.2	3.2	1.3	3.1	1.3	3.2	1.2
I24	2.6	1.3	3.2	1.2	2.9	1.3	3.2	1.3	3.0	1.2
I25	2.7	1.2	3.3	1.2	2.6	1.3	3.1	1.2	3.0	1.2
I26	3.2	1.2	3.4	1.2	3.3	1.3	3.5	1.2	3.2	1.2
I27	2.4	1.3	2.6	1.3	2.5	1.4	2.6	1.3	2.6	1.3
I28	2.9	1.2	3.4	1.1	3.1	1.2	3.2	1.2	3.4	1.1
I29	3.0	1.1	3.4	1.1	3.3	1.2	3.4	1.1	3.5	1.0
I30	2.8	1.2	3.1	1.2	2.7	1.3	3.0	1.2	3.1	1.1
Cronb. α	0.92		0.92		0.93		0.92		0.94	

TABLE A2a: Group validity tests (OLS regression models by country)

Dep. Variable: θ_1	DE	ES	IT	FR	PL
Age group					
<i>(base = 18-24 years)</i>					
25-34 years	-0.042*	0.011	0.009	-0.030	0.015
35-44 years	-0.086***	-0.007	-0.027	-0.103***	0.002
45-54 years	-0.103***	-0.044*	-0.062***	-0.135***	-0.003
55-70 years	-0.110***	-0.049**	-0.088***	-0.163***	-0.026
Gender:					
<i>(base= male)</i>					
Female	0.030***	0.035***	0.022**	0.001	0.055***
Town_size:					
<i>(base = <10.000 res.)</i>					
10.000-30.000 res.	-0.001	-0.025	0.032*	-0.016	-0.010
30.000-100.000 res.	0.015	-0.001	0.044***	0.010	-0.019
100.000-250.000 res.	0.006	0.011	0.013	0.046**	-0.035*
250.000-500.000 res.	0.031	-0.019	0.067***	-0.006	0.003
> 500.000 res.	0.011	0.008	0.033*	0.050**	0.002
N. family_members:					
<i>(base = 1 person)</i>					
2 persons	0.004	0.025	-0.040*	-0.004	-0.015
3 persons	0.020	0.058	0.002	-0.015	-0.019
4 persons	0.031	0.065	0.024	0.020	0.005
5+ persons	0.050**	0.048	0.070***	-0.002	0.023
Income_class:					
<i>(base = very low)</i>					
low	-0.020	-0.011	0.071*	0.007	-0.110**
medium-low	-0.074**	-0.048	0.020	-0.005	-0.085
medium	-0.055*	-0.051	0.047	-0.012	-0.081
medium-high	-0.021	0.020	0.050	0.010	-0.065
high	0.014	-0.011	0.110	-0.046	-0.036
very high	0.121***	0.057	0.113	0.164	0.125**
N/A	-0.061	-0.008	0.001	-0.021	-0.101
Education:					
<i>(base= Elementary school diploma)</i>					
Lower s.s. diploma	-0.017	0.007	0.037	0.017	0.003
Upper s.s. (no diploma)	0.050	-0.022	0.111	0.014	0.034
Upper s.s. diploma	-0.018	-0.012	0.031	-0.011	0.017
University (no degree)	0.027	-0.023	0.037	0.005	0.000
Bachelor's degree +	-0.008	-0.037	0.003	-0.034	-0.011
Job (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Civil state (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Constant	0.490***	0.478***	0.350***	0.530***	0.522***
N	1,018	1,016	1,053	1,012	1,025
R-squared	0.216	0.149	0.159	0.177	0.124
F-test	6.086***	3.860***	4.339***	4.727***	3.156***

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TABLE A2b: Group validity tests (OLS regression models by country)

Dep. Variable: θ_2	DE	ES	IT	FR	PL
Age group					
<i>(base = 18-24 years)</i>					
25-34 years	0.033*	0.046**	0.020	-0.008	0.011
35-44 years	0.053***	0.077***	0.011	0.007	0.040*
45-54 years	0.095***	0.113***	0.072***	0.016	0.042*
55-70 years	0.147***	0.154***	0.083***	0.078***	0.088***
Gender:					
<i>(base = male)</i>					
Female	0.042***	0.054***	0.049***	0.040***	0.057***
Town_size:					
<i>(base = <10.000 ab.)</i>					
10.000-30.000 res.	0.010	0.006	-0.006	-0.029**	0.018
30.000-100.000 res.	0.019	0.007	0.008	-0.001	0.005
100.000-250.000 res.	0.029*	0.011	0.007	0.011	0.029*
250.000-500.000 res.	0.026	0.000	0.014	-0.013	0.022
> 500.000 res.	0.016	0.012	0.015	0.021	0.041**
N. family_members:					
<i>(base = 1 person)</i>					
2 persons	-0.010	-0.016	0.002	-0.037**	-0.023
3 persons	-0.022	-0.016	-0.001	-0.045**	-0.026
4 persons	0.006	0.000	0.005	-0.030	-0.020
5+ persons	0.020	-0.040	0.032	-0.025	0.002
Income_class:					
<i>(base = very low)</i>					
low	-0.014	-0.077*	0.036	-0.009	-0.058
medium-low	-0.015	-0.079**	0.030	-0.013	0.022
medium	-0.014	-0.066*	0.051*	-0.008	0.009
medium-high	-0.003	-0.062	0.045	-0.014	-0.003
high	-0.023	-0.037	0.034	-0.021	-0.025
very high	-0.009	-0.034	0.021	0.087*	0.074
N/A	-0.088**	-0.163**	-0.003	-0.038	-0.055
Education:					
<i>(base = Elementary school diploma)</i>					
Lower s.s. diploma	0.086*	0.021	0.071	0.026	-0.023
Upper s.s. (no diploma)	0.103**	0.008	0.069	0.007	-0.026
Upper s.s. diploma	0.152***	0.066	0.085	0.043*	-0.020
University (no degree)	0.113**	0.041	0.098	0.056**	0.002
Bachelor's degree +	0.136***	0.074**	0.100	0.073***	-0.023
Job (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Civil state (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Constant	0.263***	0.474***	0.358***	0.382***	0.422***
N	1,018	1,016	1,053	1,012	1,025
R-squared	0.186	0.152	0.132	0.133	0.201
F-test	5.053***	3.966***	3.489***	3.360***	5.069***

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TABLE A2c: Group validity tests (OLS regression models by country)

Dep. Variable: θ_3	DE	ES	IT	FR	PL
Age group					
<i>(base = 18-24 years)</i>					
25-34 years	0.012	0.022	0.035	-0.026	0.025
35-44 years	-0.006	0.038	0.005	-0.074***	0.028
45-54 years	0.017	0.038	0.012	-0.077***	0.038
55-70 years	0.042*	0.077***	0.016	-0.069***	0.044
Gender:					
<i>(base= male)</i>					
Female	0.027**	0.025**	0.019*	0.000	0.051***
Town_size:					
<i>(base = <10.000 ab.)</i>					
10.000-30.000 res.	-0.004	-0.002	0.020	-0.012	0.001
30.000-100.000 res.	0.016	0.036	0.027*	0.019	-0.013
100.000-250.000 res.	0.001	0.024	0.014	0.030	-0.004
250.000-500.000 res.	0.032	-0.010	0.053**	-0.011	0.012
> 500.000 res.	0.017	0.027	0.021	0.069***	0.030
N. family_members:					
<i>(base = 1 person)</i>					
2 persons	0.011	0.012	-0.029	-0.020	-0.037*
3 persons	0.015	0.033	0.004	-0.037*	-0.033
4 persons	0.032	0.043	0.013	-0.013	-0.022
5+ persons	0.074***	0.017	0.045*	-0.010	-0.006
Income_class:					
<i>(base = very low)</i>					
low	-0.015	-0.030	0.072*	0.029	-0.058
medium-low	-0.048	-0.046	0.047	0.017	-0.028
medium	-0.013	-0.036	0.084**	0.023	-0.015
medium-high	0.016	0.019	0.092***	0.043	-0.006
high	0.022	0.003	0.132**	0.011	0.019
very high	0.082*	0.050	0.087	0.198***	0.162***
N/A	-0.015	-0.028	0.035	-0.040	-0.083
Education:					
<i>(base= Elementary school diploma)</i>					
Lower s.s. diploma	-0.036	-0.011	0.129	0.028	-0.010
Upper s.s. (no diploma)	0.000	-0.033	0.162	-0.008	0.039
Upper s.s. diploma	-0.016	0.011	0.140	-0.009	0.028
University (no degree)	0.001	-0.015	0.152	-0.004	0.006
Bachelor's degree +	-0.024	-0.006	0.134	-0.016	0.000
Job (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Civil state (dummies)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Constant	0.418***	0.438***	0.205***	0.471***	0.431***
N	1,018	1,016	1,053	1,012	1,025
R-squared	0.086	0.097	0.078	0.089	0.110
F-test	2.090***	2.358***	1.951***	2.140***	2.763***

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

B Appendix - Reliability analysis

As a first step, we perform known groups validity tests by comparing groups of consumers in each country for each of the latent characteristics of interest.

In each sub-sample (i.e. across countries) groups of consumers are compared based on the individual-level continuous measures of the three latent characteristics estimated through the MIRT-GRM model (θ_1 ; θ_2 ; θ_3). The known groups are defined using the following socio-demographic characteristics: age group, gender, number of family members, education, income class, job, civil state, and town size). We use a linear regression model to evaluate and test the statistical significance of the estimated coefficients in different groups (Tables A2a-A2c in the Appendix). As expected, the three models show that female individuals score higher compared to male individuals on the three latent characteristics across subsamples of consumers in different countries.

A positive and significant difference in the average value of θ_1 for female consumers (compared to male consumers) is observed in Germany ($\beta_F=0.030$, $p<0.01$), Spain ($\beta_F=0.035$, $p<0.01$), Italy ($\beta_F=0.022$, $p<0.1$) and Poland ($\beta_F=0.055$, $p<0.00$) except for France, where the coefficient, near to zero, does not reach statistical significance (Table A2a). Similar differences are observed on the average value of θ_2 , with female consumers scoring higher in Germany ($\beta_F=0.042$, $p<0.001$), Spain ($\beta_F=0.054$, $p<0.001$), Italy ($\beta_F=0.049$, $p<0.001$) France ($\beta_F=0.040$, $p<0.001$) and Poland ($\beta_F=0.057$, $p<0.001$) (Table A2b). Finally, significantly higher scores on θ_3 are observed for female consumers in Germany ($\beta_F=0.027$, $p<0.01$), Spain ($\beta_F=0.025$, $p<0.01$), Italy ($\beta_F=0.019$, $p<0.01$) and Poland ($\beta_F=0.051$, $p<0.001$) with the exception of France where the coefficient, near to zero, does not reach statistical significance (Table A2c). Another interesting result is related to the age groups' comparison of the three latent characteristics. Considering the average value of θ_1 the coefficients consistently decrease (assuming negative values) across groups of increasing age in all countries (except for Poland) compared to the baseline group (18-24 years). On the opposite considering the average value of θ_2 , the coefficients consistently increase across groups of increasing age in all countries. This relationship is not verified on θ_3 across countries.

Adding to the dimensionality and discriminant validity tests (see Table 4 and Table 5), we performed further tests of external validity, to establish whether the

latent constructs could be conceptualized in the same way across countries. Evidence of invariance on the meaning and the structure of the latent constructs across countries is useful to establish whether the approach (and the proposed scales for different latent constructs) is can be used in multinational research.

We tested the MIRT-GRM model separately in each country using an exploratory approach (Byrne, 2010).

Table B1 gives the goodness of fit indices for each nation.

TABLE B1 – Three-dimensional MIRT-GRM model by nation

Nation	N	M2	df	p	RMSEA	SRMSR	TLI	CFI
DE	1,018	791.84	288	0.000	0.041	0.035	0.967	0.975
ES	1,016	592.39	288	0.000	0.032	0.036	0.979	0.984
FR	1,053	586.69	288	0.000	0.032	0.036	0.984	0.988
IT	1,012	680.38	288	0.000	0.036	0.036	0.975	0.981
PL	1,025	821.40	288	0.000	0.043	0.036	0.971	0.978

The goodness of fit statistics on the different samples demonstrate that all indices fall within the boundaries outlined above (Maydeu-Olivares and Joe, 2014). Specifically, for all countries the values of RMSEA fall below the threshold of close fit ($RMSEA < 0.05$), and the values of SRMSR are indicative adequate fit ($SRMSR < 0.05$). Therefore, the model fit is acceptable for all the nations, providing evidence of invariance of the structure of the latent construct.

Further evidence of invariance on the meaning of the latent construct is reported in Table B2, reporting the estimations of MIRT-GRM parameters for the different sub-samples.

TABLE B2- Item-level estimates of the MIRT-GRM models by nation.
Discrimination parameters (α_{jv})

	DE			ES			FR			IT			PL		
	$\hat{\alpha}_{j^1}$	$\hat{\alpha}_{j^2}$	$\hat{\alpha}_{j^3}$												
I1	0.014	0.056	1.222	-0.320	0.622	1.290	-0.270	0.335	1.783	0.032	0.571	0.959	-0.331	0.540	1.409
I2	0.095	-0.372	2.623	0.395	-0.342	2.118	0.428	-0.475	2.398	0.271	-0.351	2.218	0.319	-0.278	2.878
I3	0.071	0.437	2.079	-0.253	0.452	2.167	-0.276	0.218	2.663	0.043	0.198	2.364	-0.094	0.270	2.536
I4	0.446	-0.336	1.839	0.542	-0.502	2.100	0.778	-0.049	2.043	0.782	-0.308	1.978	0.759	-0.273	2.290
I5	-0.212	0.663	1.217	-0.449	0.515	1.419	-0.469	0.585	1.501	-0.313	1.074	0.848	-0.444	0.661	1.318
I6	-0.098	0.089	2.742	0.214	-0.085	2.422	0.306	-0.184	2.834	-0.077	-0.154	2.895	0.110	-0.015	3.122
I7	0.009	-0.015	1.640	0.035	0.210	1.496	0.021	-0.152	2.152	-0.075	0.421	1.295	-0.049	0.295	1.475
I8	0.067	-0.382	2.630	0.317	-0.249	2.262	0.517	-0.163	2.527	0.088	0.143	2.052	0.368	-0.101	2.650
I9	-0.090	0.302	2.111	-0.122	0.097	1.933	-0.081	0.322	2.002	-0.139	0.417	1.898	-0.045	0.252	2.026
I10	-0.159	0.930	0.966	0.206	0.537	0.694	0.026	0.718	0.781	0.172	0.594	0.612	0.128	0.582	0.639
I11	-0.044	0.431	1.837	0.062	0.232	1.818	-0.053	0.347	1.844	0.048	0.412	1.582	0.258	0.258	1.585
I12	0.793	-0.027	1.387	1.110	-0.218	1.555	1.347	-0.040	1.386	1.384	-0.057	1.374	1.299	-0.093	1.559
I13	1.531	-0.300	0.737	1.389	0.354	0.517	1.538	0.206	0.495	1.489	0.426	0.394	1.196	0.300	0.885
I14	3.259	-2.254	0.614	2.563	-1.155	0.444	3.102	-1.143	0.492	3.053	-0.964	0.539	2.456	-0.776	0.674
I15	2.090	-0.085	0.095	1.767	0.174	0.191	1.934	0.167	0.096	1.952	0.213	-0.056	1.809	-0.049	0.432
I16	1.598	0.133	0.068	2.022	-0.264	0.372	1.584	0.190	0.036	2.202	-0.289	0.198	1.265	0.082	0.120
I17	1.865	-0.906	0.203	1.738	-0.723	0.448	2.570	-0.429	0.031	2.538	-0.521	0.241	1.475	-0.301	0.538

I18	0.467	0.917	0.522	0.336	1.415	0.125	0.445	0.987	0.354	0.257	1.293	0.163	0.368	1.388	0.188
I19	0.138	1.723	0.252	-0.228	1.439	0.523	-0.053	1.714	0.202	-0.038	1.753	0.067	0.047	1.729	0.175
I20	0.369	1.033	0.912	0.150	1.179	0.738	0.149	1.225	0.849	-0.029	1.354	0.748	-0.130	1.609	0.904
I21	0.031	1.210	0.594	-0.432	1.096	0.818	-0.268	1.405	0.598	-0.403	1.661	0.533	-0.248	1.849	0.681
I22	0.087	1.236	0.169	0.206	1.620	0.046	0.000	1.466	0.023	0.086	1.551	-0.103	-0.027	1.630	0.070
I23	1.331	0.564	-0.082	1.230	0.856	-0.039	0.944	1.050	0.010	0.998	0.541	0.025	1.117	0.903	-0.197
I24	1.015	0.134	0.135	1.054	0.612	0.064	1.101	0.533	0.014	1.067	0.746	-0.229	1.195	0.265	-0.009
I25	0.783	0.083	0.423	0.333	0.345	0.571	1.187	0.160	0.386	0.484	0.377	0.492	0.823	0.237	0.302
I26	0.842	0.527	0.206	0.432	0.377	0.564	0.748	0.726	0.277	0.587	0.586	0.311	0.842	0.560	0.256
I27	1.751	0.018	0.032	1.891	-0.076	-0.172	1.711	0.084	-0.035	1.905	-0.150	0.031	1.700	-0.104	0.130
I28	1.523	0.353	-0.070	1.367	0.742	0.091	1.196	0.510	0.106	1.488	0.519	-0.184	1.179	0.868	0.135
I29	1.050	0.663	-0.043	0.978	0.816	0.233	0.836	0.967	0.135	0.728	0.878	0.119	1.025	1.258	-0.124
I30	1.921	0.613	-0.057	2.023	0.846	0.014	1.906	0.912	0.006	1.819	0.612	-0.064	1.789	1.005	-0.065

$v=1$ for the j items on θ_1 , $v=2$ for the j items on θ_2 and $v=3$ for the j items on θ_3